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**SEOUL TO SOUL: PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF KOREAN TV DRAMAS IN THE
PURCHASE INTENTIONS OF KOREAN FOOD**

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **ALEXIS DIANE VIVIENNE L. CANDANO** with the title: **“SEOUL TO SOUL: PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF KOREAN TV DRAMAS IN THE PURCHASE INTENTIONS OF KOREAN FOOD”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

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Her understanding of the significance of multimedia in the world and society was deepened through her different exposure to multimedia-related activities. Her participation in multimedia-related internships, such as Bard College's Worldwide Teach-In on Climate and Justice Internship, exposed her to how social media can be used for professional development and societal success. Likewise, as a student member of the Multimedia Arts Association of the Philippines, Inc. (MMAAP) from January 2020 to February 2023, she has gained meaningful insights into utilizing multimedia professionally.

Furthermore, the several seminars and workshops she attended regarding digital marketing, such as the "Polytechnic University of the Philippines' (PUP) Webinar in Marketing Trends and Issues," "University of the Philippines Diliman's Circle of Entrepreneurial Academy of BizTalks 1 and 2", and "Philippine Junior Marketing Association's MadWorld: Unlocking the New Consumer Experience" gave her a deeper understanding of how multimedia and ICTs ensure business success.

Realizing the significance of the aforementioned exposure in internships, organizations, and seminars, she focused her thesis, "Seoul to Soul: Perceived Influence of Korean TV Dramas in the Purchase Intentions for Korean Food," on how Generation Z Filipinos' fascination with Korean dramas affects their consumption and purchase of Korean cuisine and food. By undertaking this research, she aims to contribute a new methodology for investigating the said topic, which will be available for use as a foundation by future researchers.

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Abstract

Owing to the Hallyu wave's extensive global influence, this study investigates the extent of K-dramas' influence on viewers' purchase intentions of Korean food. The study was conducted by surveying 110 college students in the National Capital Region in the Philippines. These students were selected as respondents because of their exposure to K-dramas and the availability of Korean food in the area. The results were analyzed using descriptive statistics and were evaluated using Elmo Lewis' AIDA Model. The success of the study depended on the use of various nominal extents, including consumption, preference, and purchase intention of Korean food.

Based on the evidence from the reviews and data collected, this study demonstrates the consumption of Korean food among viewers is positively influenced by K-dramas on Netflix. It argues that the likelihood of purchasing Korean food products is significantly correlated with how frequently people watch Korean dramas. Hence, this research makes a strong case for the influence of the Hallyu wave and the contribution of K-dramas to the promotion of Korean food consumption.

Keywords: *Hallyu*, K-dramas, Netflix, Generation Z, college students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

The Korean drama or popularly known as K-drama, catapulted onto the world stage as an Internet and social media sensation. An integral form of entertainment in South Korea, these dramas are typically long-running, episodic television series that present the lives of families or groups of people and often contain strong elements of melodrama.

In 2020, the viewership of Korean dramas jumped by 370% following the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic (Gupta, 2021). To cope with the stress and social isolation caused by the virus, many people turned to internet streaming services like Netflix and were easily fascinated by Korean dramas. Over time, the high demand for K-drama resulted in the release of more drama series that achieved large international followings, such as “Scarlet Heart,” “It’s Okay Not To Be Okay,” “Itaewon Class,” and “Vincenzo.” In fact, Netflix offers over fifty (50) different series produced by South Korean television companies.

To this day, the fascination for K-drama remains high not just as a form of entertainment but also as a source of knowledge on Korean culture, fashion, language, music, traditions, and most importantly, food. Several Korean dramas like “Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo,” “Itaewon Class,” “Hospital Playlist,” and “Wok of Love” showcased various Korean cuisines and piqued viewers’ interest to try them. To a great extent, K-drama has become a major influencer for Korean food that is prominently featured in the drama of the life of South Koreans and offered as a gift of love, a peace offering, the symbol of family traditions, and many more. Viewers around the world embraced these positively, and K-drama continues to permeate the airwaves via Netflix, YouTube, and other technology platforms in many countries like the Philippines.

Just as there is a high demand for K-drama, so is Korean food. In the Philippines, the number of Korean restaurants has risen dramatically by 81.2% as early as 2018, as reported by the Korean Food Promotion Institute (Tupas and Lee,

2020). Supermarkets and groceries exclusively selling Korean food and other merchandise have flourished in the country. In India, Korean food imports and purchases grew by 200% in 2021 (Gupta, 2021) after Korean dramas became popular with Indian audiences. This is likewise true in other Asian countries, where an increase in demand for Korean food was noted with the emergence of Korean dramas.

As stated by Tangpos (2018), Filipinos have always welcomed foreign trends and cultures. Notably, the influences of Korean culture have become ingrained in the Filipino way of life, as evidenced by their penchant for K-drama and increased consumption of Korean food. For one, the similarity in Korean and Filipino food, from steamed rice to fermented and spiced dishes, is also attributed to the patronage of Korean cuisines by Filipinos.

Indeed, with the advent of the internet and new technologies, the impact of K-drama and Korean food has grown steadily. Consuming media has become more convenient, allowing its influence to spread quickly.

Streaming platforms like Netflix have seamlessly infiltrated society, influencing and shaping people's behavior and culture. Furthermore, these platforms' pursuit of promoting different cultures by catering to different shows from around the world has piqued people's interest even further. As a result, this paved the way for influencing people's food choices and purchasing habits.

Clearly, mass media, particularly television shows, largely influences viewers' food preferences and purchases. Hence, the advent of Korean dramas raises the question of how it impacts the food habits of their audiences. While empirical studies and evidence are available, most of them are conducted among working men and women. Studies examining the impact of these television shows on Generation Z are not yet or have not been thoroughly investigated.

Moreover, the previous studies on the influence of Korean dramas primarily focused on behavior, fashion, and its general impact. The presented articles did not extend their discussion to the purchase intentions of the viewers. In this regard, the current study seeks to conduct explanatory research to fill a gap in the literature by

investigating the influence of Korean dramas on the purchase intention among the population strata Generation Z in the Philippines.

Background of the Study

South Korea has a unique traditional culture. A decade ago, this culture transitioned successfully into a popular culture in the global mainstream via its music, drama, movies, fashion, and food.

Prior to this phenomenal transition, South Korea faced a conundrum of identity crises in terms of its market penetration in the global arena. The Korean food industry struggled to reach its potential in terms of customer growth and market share. It was realized that it is important to build a strong connection between consumers and food providers in order to bridge the gap between the two and help sustain growth in this market.

The phenomenal growth of South Korea's culture and products captured world attention through the Korean wave or "*Hallyu*" in the early 1990s. At this time, the Korean food market was still at a nascent stage with limited customer awareness (Chee & Yazdanifard, 2021). The *Hallyu* captured the interests of other races in Korean drama that was perpetuated by mass and digital media like Netflix. Such interest rose significantly when Korea's largest entertainment company, CJ Entertainment & Media (CJ ENM), and its subsidiary, Studio Dragon, tied with Netflix, the major streaming platform that effectively brought Korean drama into the hearts of foreign audiences.

According to Apuke (2016), the mass media is the most persuasive in changing attitudes and behavior, as could be inferred from people's fondness for Korean drama and resultantly influence the strong liking for Korean food. Relatedly, people's perceptions and conceptions of themselves, as well as how they live their lives, are influenced by the media content they consume (Aldana, 2004, cited by Apuke, 2016).

The content and themes of Korean drama showcased the life and culture of South Koreans and prominently featured Korean food along with its culinary heritage and traditions.

The obvious influence of Korean drama is noted in the increased uptake of Korean food in many countries, the Philippines included, and in the invariable changes in consumption preferences of viewers, both the old and the young, from the generation of Baby Boomers to Generation Z, for Korean food. Fondness for Korean noodles and “bulgogi” was observed among youngsters and college students. This ignited the rise of Korean restaurants and groceries in countries where Korean drama has become the most sought-after entertainment. As years passed, the Korean food market has become increasingly competitive (Lee, 2021), as 70% of Korean food consumption notably takes place outside the country. Not surprisingly, exposure to Korean food via Korean drama impacted the way people, in particular, Generation Z, prefer or consume the food, either by eating in Korean restaurants or prepare the dish at home through online cooking demonstrations. In time, people’s preference for Korean food has become part of their lifestyle that embodies their individual and collective behavior, interests, opinions, preferences, and food choices and purchase intentions.

The high preference for Korean food is explained by the concept of cultural hybridization, which, according to Ariffin et al. (2018), is the indication of similarities in cultures of countries impact food choices and purchases. Thus, international viewers of Korean dramas see similarities in their own culture and are more likely to adopt the foreign culture. On the other hand, Iwabuchi (2002) (cited in Ariffin et al., 2018) states that cultural proximity is a factor in the successful introduction of cultural products such as food.

Indeed, besides introducing Korean culture to other countries, Korean drama contributed to propelling the global popularity of Korean food and to, a great extent, influenced the gastronomic choices of foreign cultures as well as their purchase intentions.

Executive Summary

The popularity of Korean TV dramas, or K-dramas, has rapidly spread across the world. As a result, there has been an increased interest in Korean culture and its associated products, such as fashion, music, tourism, and food. Numerous studies that looked into the impact of K-dramas have been done over time, but they mainly

concentrated on behavior, fashion, and their overall effects. Moreover, it was usually conducted among working men and women. Hence, the effects of these television programs on Generation Z have not yet or have not been fully investigated in studies.

Accordingly, the main objective of this research is to ascertain the effect of Korean dramas on Netflix on Filipino Generation Z's Korean food preferences and purchase intentions. A survey has been selected as the method for gathering data in order to meet the aforementioned goals and run the research project as efficiently as possible. Likewise, to reassure the respondents that any information shared will only be used for research, consent for the survey has been requested in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The research discovered that the consumption of K-dramas on Netflix positively influences the purchase intentions of Korean food among viewers. Statistical findings revealed a significant association between the frequency of watching Korean dramas and the likelihood of purchasing Korean food products. These findings suggest that the consumption of K-dramas indeed affects the viewers' consumption, preference, and purchase intentions and provides insights into how influential the *Hallyu* wave is and proves that K-dramas play a role in promoting the consumption of Korean food. Additionally, the area involved, nominal extents, study population, statistical analysis, and other streaming platforms are recommended for further investigation under this topic.

Statement of the Problem

The role of mass media in influencing consumer behavior is expansive. For decades, magazines, films, and television shows have influenced people's purchase intentions. This influence has grown stronger in today's society as streaming platforms have grown in popularity. As a result, it further impacted the audiences' collective behavior and attitudes toward food. Therefore, it is important to look into the impacts of this media consumption on the lifestyles of their viewers, particularly the current generation, Generation Z. Under the discipline of food, culture, and media companies, a thorough analysis is required to obtain reliable information about this rarely discussed topic in the Philippine setting. Hence, the following questions serve as a guide and research framework for the proponent in carrying out the study.

Main Problem: How do Korean dramas on Netflix affect the purchase intention of Korean food of Generation Z in the Philippines?

Sub Problems:

1. How strongly do Korean dramas influence Generation Z's Korean food consumption and preference?
2. How strongly do Korean dramas influence Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food?
3. Which Korean drama television shows influence the purchase intention of Korean food most?

Objectives

The influence of mass media, particularly Korean television shows, on the food industry is profound. Its influence grew stronger with the introduction of new technologies. Streaming platforms have become a ubiquitous part of people's lives, especially the most digitally literate generation to date, Generation Z. The main purpose of this research is to study the influence of Korean dramas presented on Netflix on the purchase intention of Korean food of Generation Z in the Philippines.

General Objectives

To determine the impact of Korean dramas on Netflix on purchase intentions and food preferences of Korean food among Generation Z in the Philippines.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the extent to which Korean dramas influence Generation Z's food choices.
2. To investigate how quickly Generation Z purchases Korean food after seeing it on Korean television shows on Netflix.

3. To determine which Korean television shows on Netflix significantly impact Generation Z's purchase intention on Korean food.

Significance of the Study

This study will present its academic and practical significance in determining the impact of Korean dramas presented on Netflix on the purchase intention of Korean food among Generation Z.

Academic Significance

With proper execution of the study design and achievement of the best results, this research is expected to contribute to understanding the effects of Korean dramas on the lifestyles of their viewers.

The research will provide data on the impact of Korean dramas on the food preferences and purchase intentions of their viewers. Furthermore, this study will also present information on how media affects viewers' consumer behavior.

Likewise, this study seeks to support the notion that South Korea acquired soft power by disseminating its culture through pop culture via media. Other stakeholders may further understand the pros and cons of South Korea's multicultural soft power brand across the globe.

If this study is successful, a new methodology for investigating the research topic will be available for use as a foundation by future researchers. Academic researchers may conduct additional research on the same industry or other relevant sectors to better understand the impact and value that the spread of Korean culture provides, as well as their positive and negative consequences.

Practical Significance

Aside from its objective to contribute significantly to academic pursuits on the topic of Korean culture and food, this study also aims to ensure that its findings will be relevant to stakeholders in media and culture.

a. Present and/or future media companies

This research aims to identify and understand the impacts of Korean dramas presented on Netflix on the purchase intention of Korean food of Generation Z in the country to serve as guidance on to which extent these media services influence their viewers' attitudes and behaviors.

b. Present and/or future audiences of the streaming platforms and television shows

This study will be critical for current users and audiences of Netflix in assessing the effects of the media they consume in their daily lives. In addition, this study will also help the streaming platform determine their television shows' impact on their audiences. Those who may have an interest in consuming these types of media content will have an idea of their benefits and complications.

c. Present and/or future researchers

Above all, this study aims to play an important role in assisting current and future researchers in understanding the impact and influence of Korean dramas presented on Netflix on their viewers. Moreover, this research could lead to further exploration of the aforementioned streaming platform or additional research into the influence of Korean culture and food preferences of Generation Z.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The primary focus of this research is the influence of Korean television series delivered on Netflix on the purchase intention of Korean food of Generation Z in the Philippines. Pursuant to this focus, the study will explain the impact of Korean television shows on the viewers' purchase decisions and food preferences. Additionally, this study will assess the collective behavior and attitudes toward Korean culture.

Defining the parameters for the respondents in this research, only the current college students from colleges and universities in the National Capital Region, Philippines, will be involved as survey respondents. It will not examine the influence of Korean television shows on Netflix unrelated to the group being studied. Thus, it will exclude other members of Generation Z who are not college students (i.e., high school students), regardless of whether Korean drama television shows on Netflix influence them. On a general note, these individuals are part of the Generation Z strata and are presumed to have a considerable amount of time on digital media usage. Accordingly, they have naturally high exposure to streaming platforms, making them useful respondents for the researcher in studying the stated mechanisms.

Additionally, to create a focused analysis and results, this study will only include selected Korean television shows such as *Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo* (2016), *Fight For My Way* (2017), *Strong Girl Bong-soon* (2017), *What's Wrong With Secretary Kim?* (2018), *Crash Landing On You* (2019), *Hospital Playlist* (2020), *Itaewon Class* (2020), *It's Okay Not To Be Okay* (2020), *Start-Up* (2020), *Run-On* (2020), *Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha* (2021), *My Roommate is a Gumiho* (2021), *Vincenzo* (2021), and *Extraordinary Attorney Woo* (2022). Thus, Korean dramas that are not on the list, regardless of whether they are available on Netflix or have influenced the respondents, will be excluded from the study.

Furthermore, the study will only involve Netflix. Other services, such as Amazon Prime, Apple TV, and Disney+ that also cater to Korean dramas are excluded. In addition, any other Korean shows, such as documentaries and variety shows, will be excluded from the study by the researcher to maintain a clear focus on the entirety of

the research. This study will not cover other materials that are solely featured on other platforms, such as broadcast television.

Meanwhile, regarding the parameter to the locus of the study, this research will take place solely in the Philippines. The researcher chose the location mainly because studies examining the aforementioned topic in the Philippines are scarce, if nonexistent. In general, given the limitations of the body of knowledge on the mentioned topic in the Philippine context, the researcher chose this locus to lay the groundwork for future research on the impact of Korean television shows on Netflix.

However, in terms of data analysis, uncontrollable factors may affect the intended data collection procedure and the overall result of the study to be executed by the researcher. These include the respondents' reluctance to discuss their consumer behavior and attitudes towards Korean television shows on Netflix and their mood when the survey questions are presented to them. Hence, implying that the study applies to all other relevant areas may be incorrect.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Rise of Korean Culture

The term *Hallyu*, or Korean wave, is a collective term that refers to South Korea's phenomenal cultural growth in the world, including the exportation of pop culture, music, TV dramas, fashion, and food. As former US President Barack Obama pointed out, South Korea has successfully marketed its culture, establishing "soft power" worldwide. According to Martin Roll (2021), South Korea is one of, if not the only, countries that have dedicated itself to becoming the world's leading exporter of its culture.

Since the 1990s, the spread of Hallyu has been consistent and exponential, with several factors playing a significant role. These factors include the release of Korean TV dramas and movies, the debut of Korean pop music and idols, the revamping of leading Korean companies, the development of the country's infrastructure, and the continuous support of their government. Accordingly, these shaped and paved the way for South Korea's success in the global market.

The popularity of Korean culture began to spread when several entertainment products created a huge buzz in the world. Firstly, the success of the introduction of K-pop as a music genre and dance paved the way for the country's breakthrough. The debut of the K-pop group "Seo Taiji and Boys" was seen as a new form of music genre. Their performance was unique at the time, making the public inclined toward their hybrid style of music. This success created a path for others to embark on, evidenced by following K-pop groups such as H.O.T., BoA, Shinhwa, Sech Kies, and others. Currently, there are numerous active K-pop groups with millions of fans worldwide. Arguably, "BTS (Bangtan Sonyeondan)," a seven-member band, is the most popular K-pop group today, snagging different music awards worldwide, including Billboard Music Awards and American Music Awards.

Furthermore, the release of various Korean TV dramas and movies maintained people's interest in Korean culture. In 1999, the movie "Swiri" about North Korean –

South Korean espionage gained tremendous popularity across Southeast Asian countries. This achievement marked the beginning of the success of Korean TV dramas and movies worldwide. Accordingly, several dramas were released to keep people's attention, including "Autumn In My Heart" in 2000, "My Sassy Girl" in 2001, and "Winter Sonata" in 2002, all of which gained traction around the world. At present, the proliferation of Korean dramas, particularly on international streaming platforms like Netflix, is patronized by many, regardless of nationality.

Moreover, the country's continued growth and popularity have been well maintained by its own products, which further boosted its potential to expand to the global scale. For instance, Samsung, a South Korean electronics company, was quick enough to pick up the cues and improve its quality, design, and branding. As a result, their improved goods were selected as one of the world's preferred electronic superior products. Martin Roll (2021) states that collectively, the acceptance and patronage of these products in the international market are heavily associated with their country of origin – South Korea. Correspondingly, this improvement became “the standard” for South Korean products. The idea was that their products and services should be developed with exceptional quality, cutting-edge designs, and a modern look. Accordingly, this new emphasis aided in sustaining the popularity of their export culture, such as entertainment media, fashion, and cuisine, which are regarded as the primary drivers of the Korean wave.

Considering all of the above evidence, these factors made South Korea and its culture appealing to the entire world. Instead of adopting the Western style, South Korea was able to shape its own cultural capitalism, both in form and nature (Ariffin et al., 2018). Thus, *Hallyu* is more than a fad; it is a cultural phenomenon (Gibson, 2021) that has permeated people's daily lives. This daily influence is exemplified by the proliferation of Korean cuisine in restaurants and grocery stores in the world's largest and most famous cities, such as New York, San Francisco, London, Paris, and Sydney, among others. Traditional Korean gourmets such as 김치 (kimchi), 불고기 (bulgogi), 짜장면 (jjajangmyeon), 삼겹살 (samgyeopsal), and 순두부찌개 (soft tofu stew) are served every day. This increase in the popularity of Korean cuisine made kimchi one of the most popular foods in America's newspaper, USA Today (Korea.net, 2021).

Synthesizing these insights, the influence of Korean culture on the world is undeniable. It was successful in various acculturating aspects of culture, including entertainment media and cuisine. As this growth and popularity continue, it will further contribute to the country's success and cater to the necessary group of audiences and consumers.

Korean Drama or K-Drama

Korean dramas are one of the factors that have kept the *Hallyu* wave alive around the world. As Chua (2010) (cited in Ariffin et al., 2018) points out, these dramas have become a staple diet for television viewers. Korean dramas are episodic television series that follow the lives of a specific group of people and frequently contain strong melodramatic elements. Accordingly, they are well-packaged forms of entertainment with strong visual and emotional appeal. Through the years, Korean dramas have gained large international audiences. In fact, Netflix, an online streaming service, caters to these audiences by offering over fifty (50) different Korean television series on its platform.

The popularity of Korean dramas started around the early 2000s when various television series such as "Winter Sonata" gained traction from international audiences. It revolved around unfortunate fates and satisfying triumphs that were relatable to household families. Korean dramas have grown in popularity over the years and now address a broader range of matters, such as sensitive issues on same-sex relationships, teenage pregnancy, and economic development. Ariffin et al. (2018) add that Korean television shows satisfy the emotional needs of audiences, particularly Asians, by assimilating similar cultural context, proximity, and expressiveness. As a result, Korean television series capture the hearts and minds of their audiences.

In 2016, Netflix produced "Mr. Sunshine", a 24-episode historical drama based on the life of Kim Young-Sam, a 19th-century Korean scholar who became a prominent figure during the tumultuous period of Japanese colonization of Korea and the fall of the Joseon dynasty. The incredible cinematography of its high-quality production astounded the entertainment industry, radically altering the landscape for future

Korean dramas (Moeller, 2022). Correspondingly, Korean dramas and films were consistently produced, breaking record after record.

This success stems from striking a balance between the predictability and originality (de Witte, 2021) of the stories. It has a standard plot in which the main characters go through a painful narrative before reaching happy endings. However, its Korean twist of presenting the characters as attractive, filial, and relatable makes it worthy of a 16-hour binge-watch. Moreover, Korean dramas are lavishly funded in order to showcase their culture and create an enjoyable viewing experience. Thus, audiences are assured of getting a slice of Korean culture, such as tradition, scenery, and food.

Furthermore, Korean dramas expose audiences to new and different concepts they have never seen before. Notably, the shows “Kingdom,” “Sweet Home,” and “All of Us Are Dead” showcase a new realm of zombies, monsters, and dark fantasies (Moeller, 2022). As a result, these shows received recognition from across the globe, particularly in the States and Europe. Another Korean series that gained worldwide acclaim is “Squid Game.” Its unique plot and concept helped it become the most-watched series on Netflix, with 95% of its viewers coming from outside Korea (Moeller, 2022). It was dubbed the “golden gatekeeper” of the Korean entertainment industry after receiving numerous awards from various countries, including Emmy Awards.

This Korean drama craze is popular among people of all ages, especially millennials and Generation Z. In a study conducted by Dunan et al. (2022), they found that the intense exposure of Indonesian millennials and Generation Z to Korean dramas created a huge interest in learning the Korean language. The study revealed that this desire stemmed from an objective of understanding the show without subtitles, which was fueled by the Korean dramas’ exciting storylines, stunning cinematography, and compelling actors and actresses. This argument is supported by Indrawan et al. (2020), who claimed that Generation Z in Indonesia changed their lifestyle and language style due to Korean dramas. According to their study, some adolescent Indonesians use Korean words in everyday conversations. Likewise, they assert that aside from language, these Korean dramas influence Generation Z Indonesians’

behaviors. Examples of these behaviors are executed through imitation of food, clothing styles, and make-up.

Given these facts, it is undeniable that Korean content is sweeping the entertainment industry and influencing people in countries all over the world. As audiences plunge themselves into these television shows, they are most likely to acquire and adopt several values and practices. To some extent, these include purchases and choices in food.

Generation Z

Generation Z (aka Gen Z) refers to the population strata born between 1997 and 2012. As stated by Chicca and Shellenbarger (2018) (cited in Park and Chun, 2020), this generation is considered well-versed in digital culture. They grew up in a world with the Internet, gadgets, and digital media. Thus, they are confident in using new technologies to accomplish certain tasks and interact with other people, making them digital natives. As Adecco (2015) (cited in Park and Chun, 2020) puts it, Gen Z members are good at multitasking, processing, and accessing information in the digital world.

Given this digital exposure, their social media usage has become an integral part of their daily lives. Hence, their behaviors, attitudes, and preferences are highly influenced by what they see online. Park and Chun (2020) posit that they obtain related and relevant information from social media platforms. As they use social media daily and immerse themselves in these platforms, they adapt to different foreign cultures and traditions. This occurrence explains the wide understanding of Gen Zs to different issues in society and the world.

Moreover, this generation's consumers are perceived to be always on top of the latest trends. It is common to see Gen Zs post on social media platforms with different hashtags, indicating the most recent topics and trends worldwide. Hence, members of this population stratum are afraid of the feeling of being left behind or fear of missing out (FOMO). According to Bautista (2020), this FOMO feeling is linked to the increased television viewing habits of the younger generation. This proclivity for

the latest trends stems from a desire to participate in a cultural conversation (Conlin et al., 2016; cited in Bautista, 2020). This generation is interested in remaining relevant and connected to the "in-the-moment" aspect of their choices and preferences.

In terms of the consumer habits of Generation Z, they are interested in finding deals and discounts before they shop. According to Kim et al. (2020), 66% of Gen Zs in Australia and 50% of Gen Zs in China look for bargains before making purchases. Likewise, their purchasing decisions are heavily affected by what they watch, which influences how they choose brands and products. Majority of Gen Zs in Australia, China, Indonesia, Thailand, Japan, and South Korea shares that their purchase decisions are impacted by video-based media (Kim et al., 2020).

In conclusion, while there have been a few studies on the general behavior and actions of Generation Z members, the global academe must invest more in learning more about this stratum of individuals in different parts of the world. These people will not only make up the majority of society in the coming years, but they will also enable growth and development in various fields. For instance, having extensive knowledge of their food preferences will help future marketers and businesses to create products that interest them.

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention, according to Buchari Alma (2019) (cited in Sembiring & Prabandari, 2021), refers to a consumer's decision that is influenced by a variety of factors such as the economy, technology, culture, products, prices, financial status, location, and people. Machfoedz (2013) (cited in Fortuna & Marwati, 2021) adds that it is a process of analyzing and choosing from different options based on specific interests, with the goal of making the most profitable choice. This is further supported by Schiffman & Kanuk (2019) (cited in Sembiring & Prabandari, 2021), who stated that purchase intent is defined as a choice between two or more alternatives. Thus, purchase intent is determined by a number of options based on particular available considerations.

On the other hand, Daneshvary & Schower (2000) (cited in Shan et al., 2019) states that purchase intention is also influenced by the consumer's demographics, such as sex, age, education, and social class. To support this, Vilcekova and Sabo (2013) noted that demographic characteristics play an important role in a consumer's purchase intention as they affect the motivation and attitudes toward a product.

From a unique perspective, Wang & Yang (2008) (cited in Shan et al., 2019) affirms that a consumer's purchase intention can be determined based on the product itself. Based on this claim, consumers' purchase decisions are affected by their critical attitudes.

Furthermore, as stated by Fortuna & Marwati (2021), culture influences consumer purchasing intentions. Culture refers to customs, politics, religion, language, and clothing. This claim is supported by Santoso & Purwanti (2013) (cited in Fortuna & Marwati, 2021), asserting that culture is the most fundamental influencer of desires and behavior. Today's culture can be transmitted through virtual platforms through the internet and social media. For instance, the thorough study of Sun & Sing (2022) showed that Generation Z's active cultural sharing and exchanging on social media affected their purchase intentions. Accordingly, it is evident that culture plays a significant role in consumer preferences and purchase intentions.

These consumer behaviors are manifested through purchases made by people influenced by a certain culture. According to Han et al. (2021), the widespread consumption of Korean wave content, such as K-drama and K-pop, increased the intent of consumers to purchase Korean products. Kim et al. (2014) (cited in Choi et al., 2022) state that there are several factors that affect the consumers' purchase intention of Korean products; these are value consciousness, trust, the importance of origin, and attitude toward Korean goods.

Studies conducted by Chee & Yazdanifard (2021) and Sembiring et al. (2021) claim that the high selection and inclination of Malaysians and Indonesians to Korean restaurants and cuisine are caused by the people's positive perception of Korean culture. The researchers declare that this proclivity is due to the elevated attention of Malaysian and Indonesian consumers to Korean dramas, films, and K-pop. This

observation proves that appreciation of culture affects consumer purchasing decisions. Similar to this analysis, Khai & Hang (2019) (cited in Astuti & Asih, 2021) states that the cultural influence of Korean dramas and Korean celebrities causes these behavioral intentions to try and purchase Korean cuisine.

Related to this, Son and Kijboonchoo (2016) discuss that purchase intention is also significantly influenced by where products are manufactured. Hence, a consumer's perception of a country affects their attitude towards a product being presented and sold. This action is backed up by studies conducted by Yasin et al. (2007) (cited in Son and Kijboonchoo, 2016) and Halim & Zulkarnain (2017) (cited in Astuti & Asih, 2021), which state that a consumer's decision to purchase is impacted by their evaluation of a product's country of origin. Thus, the increase in purchase intentions of foreign products is correlated with the consumer's impressions of the product's country of origin. Astuti & Asih (2021) pointed out that the "country-of-origin image" heavily influences consumer purchase intentions of Korean products in Indonesia.

In conclusion, consumers purchase products based on their ideas or experiences that satisfy their needs and wants (Kother & Armstrong, 2019; cited in Sembiring & Prabandari, 2021). Cultural exchange, the country of origin of the product, and the consumer's impressions of that country all influence the consumer's purchase intentions. Thus, it could be deduced that these factors influenced the increase of foreign products, specifically food, in different countries. Accordingly, proper strategizing of these factors is vital to the success of products' exportation.

Consumer Behavior of Foreign Products

Consumer behavior is the process by which individuals make choices about what to buy and how much they are willing or able to pay for it. It can be viewed as a way to satisfy wants and needs. Castillo (2018) states that in the Philippines, the attitude-behavior consistency (ABC) factor plays a very important role in shaping consumer behavior. This means that how customers feel about a product influences their purchasing decisions. For instance, if a person likes a particular product because it is of high quality and suits their needs, they are likely to buy it regardless of the price.

On the other hand, if a person is hesitant about a product because of its price, it will affect their decision to buy it (Adobo Magazine, 2018). In general, people tend to be consistent in their attitudes and behaviors. Thus, consumers tend to buy products based on their perceived value and quality. Following that, other factors also influence consumer behavior, including demographics, status, and environment.

In a study conducted by Wang and Lee (cited in Han et al., 2021), the increased attention gained by Korean products on social networking sites affected the purchasing behavior and decisions of Chinese female consumers. This demonstrates how a consumer's environment has a significant impact on their intention to buy foreign goods, in this case, a Korean product.

Furthermore, Moschis (1976) (cited in Mustafa & Rifat, 2019) argued that additional elements influence consumer behavior, including personal motivations, past experiences, and cultural influences. As such, research suggests that sociocultural differences among countries affect consumer behavior. In other words, culture plays a key role in determining how people behave and how they make buying decisions. For instance, Asian cultures often prefer products that are functional and practical, while Western cultures prefer products that are attractive (Ugarte, 2020). Evidently, these cultural differences have an impact on how consumers in various parts of the world perceive different products.

Considering the Philippines, a culturally diverse country that has been influenced by different cultures and religions over the years has resulted in Filipinos having different consumer behaviors when it comes to foreign products. Filipino consumers are known to be "middle-market centered" (Open to Export, 2017), and when they see something they like, they buy it even if it is not available locally.

In summary, it is evident that Filipinos' attitude toward foreign products has an undeniable influence on their consumer behaviors. Likewise, their consumer behavior is segmented in terms of their demographics, social class, and environment. Nevertheless, as long as the country continues to import foreign products, Filipinos will continue to buy them. Thus, it is critical to understand what motivates them to purchase such products regardless of price.

Theoretical Framework

This research study will be anchored on two postulations, namely: the Theory of Planned Behavior and the AIDA Model.

General Theory: Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior serves as the theoretical foundation for this research endeavor. This theory, proposed by Icek Ajzen in 1991, contends that behavioral intention is influenced by attitude toward the behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control (Sansom, 2022). The model, as illustrated below, depicts a framework for the factors that influence people's behavior.

Figure 1: The Theory of Planned Behavior. (1991). Retrieved from Sansom (2022).

Based on Figure 1, the behavioral intention of a person is influenced by certain factors such as attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Thus, the stronger these factors influence a person, the more likely that person will engage in that behavior.

According to the theory, the first construct is the “attitudes” factor, which refers to an individual’s evaluation of such behavioral consequences. This construct is subjective and may result in a positive or negative assessment of a particular behavior. Hence, an individual's attitude toward a particular behavior has a direct impact on their

intention to engage in that behavior. The second is “subjective norms”, or the social situational factor of the theory. This refers to the social pressure to engage or refrain from engaging in a particular behavior. This construct describes whether other members of a group approve or disapprove of certain behavior. Lastly, a person’s behavioral intention is influenced by perceived behavioral control. This describes a person's perception of the desired behavior's ease or difficulty.

This theory is related to the research project because the former discussed how certain factors influence people's behavioral intentions. The theory of planned behavior is useful in understanding certain aspects that influence consumer purchasing intentions and behaviors for Korean food products. Moreover, this theory will assist the researcher in determining the various perspectives of consumer deciding factors.

Currently, the prevalence of Korean drama across nations is undeniable. It has a strong effect on a consumer's decision to purchase Korean food. Thus, the researcher believes that the theory of planned behavior will help to determine the various attitudes, social factors, and considerations of consumers.

Specific Theory: The AIDA (Awareness/Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) Model

The AIDA model was devised by Elmo Lewis in the 1800s proposes that a consumer goes through different phases before purchasing a product or service (Sellers, 2021). This model contends that a product attracts attention and generates interest from the consumer; it most likely creates a conviction to purchase the product or service. For instance, televised advertisements grab the attention of consumers which ultimately invokes interest in the product and compels them to purchase (Communication Theory, 2014). The AIDA Model is depicted in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: The AIDA Model. (1800). Retrieved from Sellers (2021).

As discussed by the AIDA Model, there are four stages that a consumer goes through before purchasing a product or service: awareness/attention, interest, desire, and action. Although the model's stages are sequential, as presented in the diagram, the researcher intends to investigate the possibility of gaining additional stages.

Chee & Yazdanifard (2021) state that the South Korean government purposely aimed to introduce their culture by showcasing their food to international audiences. They believe that food represents culture, enticing people to experience a country's way of life. Hence, in an ideal setting, every Korean drama strives to attract viewers' attention by displaying and eating Korean food in scenes. It attempts to move a potential customer by catching their attention to the act of purchasing the product being showcased.

The AIDA model is relevant to the research topic because it seeks to identify a specific measure of influence that Korean dramas exert on their audiences. Similarly, the stages of the AIDA model can be used by the researcher to determine which stage Korean dramas are reaching in order to attract and entice viewers to buy Korean food products featured in the shows.

Overall, these theories are related to the study being conducted because they discuss how certain factors influence the preferences, attitudes, and perceptions of people. Moreover, these postulations investigate the extent of exposure to a stimulus,

which will aid the researcher in demonstrating a link between streaming Korean dramas and Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food.

Conceptual Framework

This study will mainly focus on the influence of Korean dramas streamed on Netflix on the audiences' purchase intentions and consumer behaviors. It should be noted that the literature presented focused on the study's major data and background information, such as the global influence of Korean dramas and Generation Z behavior in general. Hence, the main information will come from the influence of Korean dramas on its viewers.

Figure 3: The Conceptual Framework for the Study

As seen in the framework, this endeavor is guided by Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior and Lewis' AIDA Model. The researcher intends to collect data using a quantitative research approach exemplified by self-administered surveys. Having the demographic characteristics of Generation Z individuals as the intervening variables, the researcher seeks to describe the relationship between the influence of Korean dramas and Gen Z's purchase intention of Korean food. Through this framework and approach, the proponent expects to gain knowledge to arrive at a myriad of similarities and differences in answers and to write a logical summary of the results.

The summary, conclusion, and recommendation regarding the study's main findings will round out the research project. The inquiry's output will focus on

information about the intentions of consumers' Korean food purchases and preferences. All of the discussions will contribute to the context-based development of a specific body of knowledge about the relationship between Korean dramas streamed on Netflix to the purchase intentions of Korean food of Generation Z college students in the Philippines.

Operational Definitions

1. **consumer behavior** – [technical definition] the study of how people make purchasing decisions to meet their needs and desires (Schofield & Schalia, 2021).
2. **college students** – [operational definition] the population strata from which the respondents of the study will be pulled from.
3. **Generation Z** – [technical definition] individuals born between 1997 and 2012 who have grown up in a world with the internet, digital media, and gadgets, with some attending and graduating from college by 2020 (Meola, 2022).
4. **Hallyu wave** – [technical definition] the term used to describe the popularity of Korean culture, such as K-pop music and K-dramas (Haugland, 2020).
5. **Korean drama** – [operational definition] South Korean episodic television series in the Korean language that is aired on streaming platforms.
6. **Korean food** – [operational definition] the cuisine, which refers to the traditional foods of Korea that are bought by the respondents.
7. **Netflix** – [technical definition] an American streaming service that offers original movies, award-winning television shows, and documentaries.
8. **purchase intention** – [technical definition] the degree to which consumers are interested in buying the product or service within a specific time frame (Survey Monkey, 2022).

9. **streaming platform** – [operational definition] an entertainment source for television shows, movies, documentaries, and anime delivered via internet-connected devices (e.g., phones, tablets, personal computers).
10. **television shows/series** – [operation definition] any content created for television viewing over the Internet.

Hypotheses

In this regard, the researcher developed the following hypotheses, which will be proven or disproven after the study.

H1: Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects Generation Z's Korean food preferences and consumption.

H2: Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food.

H3: Certain Korean dramas on Netflix influence Generation Z's food preferences and purchase intentions for Korean food.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A causal-explanatory design will be used in this study to examine the relationship between watching Korean dramas and Generation Z's Korean food preferences and purchase intentions. A causal-explanatory study investigates and assesses whether two distinct instances have a cause-and-effect relationship (George & Merkus, 2021).

This procedure is academically appropriate in this research because it helps ensure the accuracy and specificity of any results disclosed by the researcher. It emphasizes the objectives of representing Filipino Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food as influenced by Korean dramas on Netflix. Likewise, it will aid in the discovery or development of patterns and trends in existing data, resulting in a better understanding of the topic.

In addition, the researcher recognizes that each participant is exposed to a different environment. Hence, collected data are expected to have complexity and subjectivity depending on context. Moreover, the responses collected will be compared side-by-side to see if there are any similarities and/or differences that can be used to provide a logical conclusion and evaluation of the results. Overall, the design of this endeavor will place a premium on accurately portraying Generation Z college students as consumers who react differently to the Korean dramas that are presented to them.

Locale of the Study

The research will be carried out in various colleges and universities within the National Capital Region. This locale is chosen as the researcher underscores the convenience of reaching the respondents from time to time. Likewise, the researcher presumes that most of the respondents from this area have access to Netflix. These factors, as per the researcher, make the research project more feasible to complete.

Respondents of the Study

This research endeavor will primarily focus on the current college students in the National Capital Region, Philippines. The stated students are part of a particular generation stratum called Generation Z, which is immersed in various forms of digital technology such as televisions, cell phones, computers, and the Internet. Hence, they are presumed to have consumed content on the mentioned streaming platform (i.e., Netflix). The unit of analysis was chosen to be neither too precise nor too imprecise in order to retain the necessary context for interpreting the data. This specific categorization will also avoid obscure meanings and erroneous conclusions.

Variables and Measures

Variables

The independent variables in this study are the treatments under the researcher's control, such as subjects' exposure to Korean television shows on Netflix. The intervening variables which could potentially affect the relationship between the independent and dependent variables include the demographic profile of the respondents as well as their usage of streaming services. The dependent variables to be evaluated in this research are the respondents' food preferences, consumer behavior, and purchase intentions. The next sections of this chapter will provide a further discussion of the treatment, gathering, and assessment of these variables.

Figure 4: Variables of the Study

Measures

As mentioned above, this study will collect quantitative data using a causal-explanatory design. A descriptive research survey will be conducted in this study to gather quantitative data. Descriptive research surveys produce reliable data that define a group's opinions, attitudes, and behaviors on a given subject (Survey Monkey, 2022). The survey will contain ratio variables in the form of questions with multiple sets of possible responses to measure the respondents' usage and parameters of Korean drama consumption.

Given this, it will assist the researcher in determining and describing the preferences, similarities, differences, and characteristics of respondents in the sample, allowing the researcher to derive analytical conclusions from the data results. Moreover, this design was chosen because survey research can be completed quickly by participants on the same day it is given to them.

Sampling Procedure

The sample for this study is presumed to have watched Korean dramas on Netflix. The chosen research population is college students in the Philippines who have watched shows from at least three Korean dramas on Netflix. These respondents will be selected using probability sampling, called stratified sampling. Stratified sampling entails the researcher randomly choosing a subset of participants from a population (Thomas, 2020b). The researcher emphasizes the ease of reaching the respondents because the researcher is also a member of Generation Z, which includes the aforementioned target participants. Hence, the researcher presumes that these students have watched at least three Korean dramas on Netflix. The total target sample size is 100 respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The chosen participants will not be forced to participate in this research study as data sources. They will be informed that their participation in this study is entirely voluntary. Similarly, the respondents will be notified about the nature and purpose of the study. In line with this, the proper use and confidentiality of any information will be ensured during questionnaire distribution. Finally, the collected data will be further assessed using the specific modes of analysis discussed in the following section.

Primary Data

For efficient distribution and communication, the researcher opts to conduct surveys online to collect data.

Specifically, the researcher will utilize online data-gathering websites such as Google Forms or Survey Monkey. The survey forms will be distributed randomly to respondents across various social media platforms, including Facebook, Messenger, Twitter, Instagram, and Discord. These college students will be informed that answering the questionnaire is entirely voluntary, and they are free to withdraw if they become uncomfortable while responding for any reason. Their participation will not

affect the relationship they have, if any, with the researcher. Following this, the researcher will analyze the collected data using the specific modes of analysis below.

Secondary Data

To address the research topic, the researcher also used secondary sources of information, selecting the most relevant online foreign journal studies and articles and other credible online references. The majority can be found in the paper's literature review section, which focuses on subtopics such as The Rise of Korean Culture, K-Drama, Generation Z, Purchase Intention, and Consumer Behavior toward Foreign Products.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the research questionnaires completed by the college students will be converted into statistical percentages and measures of central tendencies. The factors influencing college students' Korean food purchase intentions and preferences will be calculated quantitatively from the central tendency of the nominal-minded and scale-based questions.

Frequency Percentage Formula

The frequency and sample size will be determined using the Frequency Percentage Formula. The percentage is calculated by dividing the frequency by the sample size and multiplying it by 100%.

$$F\% = \left(\frac{f}{n}\right)100$$

Where:

$F\%$ = Frequency Percentage

f = frequency

n = sample size

Measures of Central Tendency

The measures of central tendency will be used to interpret responses to yes-no, nominally-minded, and scale-based questions. The researcher will apply the “50% + 1” rule to determine the superior and representative answers for the sample of respondents. Two specific measures of central tendency will be highlighted, namely the mean and the mode.

$$\mu = \frac{\Sigma x}{N}$$

Where:

μ = population mean

Σx = observed values

N = number of observations in the population

$$Mode = l + \left(\frac{f_0 - f_1}{2f_1 - f_0 - f_2} \right) \times h$$

Where:

l = lower limit of the modal class

h = size of the class interval

f_1 = frequency of the modal class

f_0 = frequency of the class preceding the modal class

f_2 = frequency of the class succeeding the modal class

Weighted Arithmetic Mean

The average of each value weighted differently will be calculated using the Weighted Arithmetic Mean. It will help in determining the levels of purchasing decisions and behaviors of the respondents.

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma xw}{\Sigma w}$$

Where:

$\bar{X}$ = mean

x = measurement of value

w = number of measurements

Weighted Average	Result	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Influential
3.40 - 4.19	Agree	Influential
2.60 - 3.39	Neutral	Neutral
1.80 - 2.59	Disagree	Uninfluential
1.00 - 1.79	Strongly Disagree	Very Uninfluential

Figure 5: Explanation of Weighted Mean Values

Cronbach's Alpha Test

The Cronbach's Alpha test gauges how closely related a group of variables are to one another internally and in terms of scale reliability (University of California Los Angeles, 2016).

$$\alpha = \frac{N\bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (N - 1)\bar{c}}$$

Where:

α = coefficient alpha

N = number of items

$\bar{c}$ = average inter-item covariance between data variables

$\bar{v}$ = average variance

<i>Internal Consistency</i>	<i>Internal Consistency</i>
Excellent	$\alpha \geq 0.9$
Good	$0.9 \geq \alpha \geq 0.8$
Acceptable	$0.8 \geq \alpha \geq 0.7$
Questionable	$0.7 \geq \alpha \geq 0.6$
Poor	$0.6 \geq \alpha \geq 0.5$
Unacceptable	$0.5 \geq \alpha$

Source: George and Mallery (2003)

Figure 6: Interpretation of Cronbach's Alpha Values. Retrieved from George and Mallery, 2003, cited in Zulhelmi et al., 2017.

Furthermore, to graphically illustrate the responses, frequency distribution tables will be used. This is to ensure better visualization of the totality of responses collected, allowing the researcher to present the quantitative data in the study objectively and professionally. These diagrams will be accompanied by descriptions and short discussion paragraphs highlighting the visible peaks, lows, and various points representing the students' responses.

Validity and Reliability

To confirm the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test survey was carried out. This aided the researcher in determining whether the prepared questions were pertinent to the subject under discussion and were understood by the respondents. The initial questionnaire had a total of fourteen (14) questions for Likert-scale type of questions and was subjected to a Cronbach's Alpha reliability test. Reliability Statistics of Korean Food Consumption and Preference resulted in eight (8) items (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.912268314 ~ 0.91), and Reliability Statistics of Korean Food Purchase Intention having six (6) items (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.921938918 ~ 0.92). The pre-test survey was answered by ten (10) respondents.

Following the pilot test, the questionnaire was modified based on the results and some suggestions from the respondents. Accordingly, some modifications to the question structures were made to yield more straightforward answers.

Ethical Considerations

On the surface, ethics refers to moral standards that prescribe what humans should do, typically in terms of rights, fairness, and obligations (Velasquez et al., 2020). In the context of research, ethics are a set of principles and virtues that guide researchers in collecting data from people in accordance with a specific code of conduct (Bhandari, 2021). Hence, ethical considerations undertake to conduct research with just and harmless actions. In line with this, researchers must obtain permission or consent from participants for how the data collected will be used in the endeavor (Fleming & Zegwaard, 2018).

As the endeavor's goals revolve around understanding life experiences, investigating habits, and exploring behaviors, ethical considerations for the study are heavily weighed in order to protect its subjects.

Hence, with respect to these guidelines, the researcher intends to ensure the respondents that participating in the study is entirely voluntary. If the respondents feel uncomfortable during the data collection, they are free to withdraw. Their participation will have no bearing on their relationship, if any, with the researcher. Similarly, their provided data will not be included in the research endeavor. Furthermore, potential participants are given a brief overview of the research topic before data collection begins. This ensures that no potential participants are coerced into participating in the study. In addition, the researcher guarantees the respondents that all data and information collected are confidential and used solely for research purposes.

The questionnaire will be carefully crafted to keep it brief and simple so that respondents only provide information relevant to the study. Likewise, to ensure sensitivity between the researcher and the respondents, the questionnaire will be posed professionally and appropriately.

Following the completion of the study, the researcher will express gratitude to the respondents for their time and effort in participating in the study. Most importantly, the participants will be informed of the findings and outcomes of the endeavor once they have been academically approved.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proponent was able to gather primary data from 110 college students in the National Capital Region who voluntarily participated in the study and completed the distributed online survey questionnaire (via Google Forms). The following requirements were met by the respondents: they were between the ages of 18 and 25; they were enrolled in college in the National Capital Region; they have consumed at least three of the listed Korean foods (i.e., samgyupsal, kimchi, ramyeon, Korean fried chicken, odeng, gimbap, bibimbap, tteokbokki, sundubu jiggae, jokbal, bibimguksu, miyeokguk, bunggeopang, gyeran-mari, jangjorim, sundae); and they have watched at least three of the listed Korean dramas on Netflix (i.e., Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016), Fight For My Way (2017), Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017), What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018), Crash Landing On You (2019), Hospital Playlist (2020-2021), Itaewon Class (2020), It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020), Start-Up (2020), Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021), My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021), Vincenzo (2021), and Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)).

The purpose of the study is to determine whether Korean dramas affect the purchase intention of Korean food of Generation Z (in this case, current college students) in the Philippines. Thus, to achieve a detailed understanding of the topic, the proponent used a causal-explanatory research design. A thorough presentation of the findings from the survey will be provided in the tables and sections that follow.

Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents

Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18	4	3.6
19	3	2.7
20	22	20
21	27	24.5
22	36	32.7
23	12	10.9
24	4	3.6

25	2	1.8
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 1: Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents: Age.

As shown in **Table 1**, out of one hundred ten respondents, the age group "22" has the highest frequency, with a total of thirty-six respondents; twenty-seven college students fall within the "21" age bracket, while twenty-two respondents fall within the "20" age bracket, and twelve respondents fall within the "23" age bracket. While each of the age groups "24" and "18" has four respondents, "19" has three, and "25" has two. These data attest to the respondents' membership in the Generation Z group, which is referred to frequently in the research paper.

Sex assigned at birth

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	87	79.1
Male	23	20.9
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 2: Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents: Sex assigned at birth.

Table 2 reveals that the majority of responses (eighty-seven) were female, with males accounting for the remaining twenty-three.

Current Location

Current Location	Frequency	Percentage
Quezon City	41	37.3
Manila	29	26.4
Caloocan	11	10
Makati	6	5.5
Valenzuela	5	4.5
Taguig	4	3.6
Marikina	4	3.6

Pasay	3	2.7
Malabon	2	1.8
Paranaque	2	1.8
Muntinlupa	2	1.8
Pasig	1	0.9
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 3: Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents: Current Location.

The respondents are spread out throughout the National Capital Region, with 37.3% reporting to be in Quezon City, 26.4% in Manila, 10% in Caloocan, 5.5% in Makati, and 4.5% in Valenzuela. Others are located in Taguig (3.6%), Marikina (3.6%), Pasay (2.7%), Malabon (1.8%), Paranaque (1.8%), Muntinlupa (1.8%), and Pasig (0.9%). These data confirm that the respondents are currently located in the National Capital Region.

Current College or University

Current College or University	Frequency	Percentage
University of Santo Tomas	22	20
Far Eastern University	15	13.63
Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila	12	10.90
Technological University of the Philippines	7	6.36
University of the Philippines	6	5.45
Polytechnic University of the Philippines	6	5.45
De La Salle University	5	4.54
Manila Central University	5	4.54
World Citi Colleges	5	4.54
University of Caloocan	4	3.63
Centro Escolar University	3	2.72
CIIT College of Arts and Technology	3	2.72
Philippine Women's University	2	1.81
Rizal Technological University	2	1.81

AMA University	1	0.90
Ateneo de Manila University	1	0.90
Emilio Aguinaldo College	1	0.90
Lyceum of the Philippines University	1	0.90
Makati Science Technological Institute of the Philippines	1	0.90
Miriam College	1	0.90
National Teachers College	1	0.90
New Era University	1	0.90
Our Lady of Fatima University	1	0.90
STI College	1	0.90
Technological Institute of the Philippines	1	0.90
University of the East	1	0.90
University of Makati	1	0.90
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 4: Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents: Current College or University.

As seen in **Table 4**, the respondents study in different reputable universities and colleges in the National Capital Region. 20% of those polled indicated they are enrolled in the University of Santo Tomas, followed by 13.63% at Far Eastern University, 10.90% at Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila, 6.36% at the Technological University of the Philippines, 5.45% at the University of the Philippines and Polytechnic University of the Philippines, 4.54% at De La Salle University, Manila Central University, and World Citi Colleges, 3.63% at the University of Caloocan, 2.72% at Centro Escolar University and CIIT College of Arts and Technology, 1.81% at Philippine Women’s University and Rizal Technological University and 0.90% at AMA University, Ateneo de Manila University, Emilio Aguinaldo College, Lyceum University of the Philippines, Makati Science Technological Institute of the Philippines, Miriam College, National Teachers College, New Era University, Our Lady of Fatima University, STI College, Technological Institute of the Philippines, University of the East, and University of Makati. These numbers demonstrate that the survey respondents are currently enrolled in universities in the National Capital Region.

Current Year Level

Current Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
1st Year	9	8.2
2nd Year	19	17.3
3rd Year	30	27.3
4th Year	48	43.6
5th Year	3	2.7
6th Year	1	0.9
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 5: Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents: Current Year Level.

The majority of respondents, 43.6%, said they were in their fourth year of college, followed by 27.3% in their third year, 17.3% in their second year, 8.2% in their first year, 2.7% in their fifth year, and 0.9% in their sixth year.

Screeners Questions

When did you start watching Korean dramas (K-dramas) on Netflix?

Year	Frequency	Percentage
2016	53	48.2
2017	10	19.1
2018	11	10
2019	18	16.4
2020	14	12.7
2021	3	2.7
2022	1	0.9
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 6: Screener Question: Year started watching K-dramas.

For the first preliminary question, 48.2% of the respondents stated that they started watching K-dramas on Netflix in 2016, thereby indicating they began watching

K-dramas the same year Netflix began offering K-dramas on their platform. Meanwhile, the second dominant response for this question was 2019, getting 16.4%.

How often do you watch Korean dramas (K-Dramas) on Netflix?

Occurrence	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	12	10.9
Once a week	8	7.3
Twice a week	13	11.8
Thrice a week	28	25.5
Once a month	26	23.6
Once every 3 months	14	12.7
Once every 6 months	8	7.3
Once every 12 months	1	0.9
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 7: Screener Question: K-drama viewing frequency.

According to **Table 7**, 25.5% of respondents said they watch K-dramas on Netflix at least three times per week, while 23.6% say they only do so once a month. These results minimally or partially support the researcher’s presumption that it is highly likely that viewers are more influenced by K-dramas when they watch them more frequently.

How many hours do you spend per day watching Korean dramas (K-dramas) on Netflix?

Hours	Frequency	Percentage
Less than an hour	6	5.5
1 - 2 hours	19	17.3
3 - 6 hours	62	56.4
7 - 9 hours	16	14.5
10 - 12 hours	3	2.7

More than 12 hours	4	3.6
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 8: Screener Question: Time spent watching K-dramas.

Based on **Table 8**, 56.4% of respondents state they spend at least 3-6 hours watching K-dramas on Netflix. Concurrently, the following dominant responses for this question are 1-2 hours and 7-9 hours, with 17.3% and 14.5%, respectively. These findings highlight the proponent's hypothesis that K-dramas have a greater impact on the more hours viewers (in this case, college students in the National Capital Region) watch them.

Which of the following K-dramas have you watched on Netflix? (Select all that apply).

Korean Dramas	Frequency	Percentage
Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)	89	80.9
Fight For My Way (2017)	67	60.9
Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017)	72	65.5
What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018)	70	63.6
Crash Landing On You (2019)	77	70
Hospital Playlist (2020-2021)	37	33.6
Itaewon Class (2020)	69	62.7
It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020)	65	59.1
Start-Up (2020)	60	54.5
Run-On (2020)	19	17.3
Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021)	56	50.9
My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021)	46	41.8
Vincenzo (2021)	58	52.7
Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)	70	63.6

Table 9: Screener Question: Frequently viewed K-dramas.

Table 9 shows that at least 60% of respondents have seen every single one of the K-dramas that were specifically chosen and included in the survey. This also

supports the researcher's assumption that, given the popularity of these K-dramas, Generation Z viewers have watched them.

Which of the following Korean food have you eaten? (Select all that apply).

Korean Food	Frequency	Percentage
삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue	108	98.2
오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake	93	84.5
순대 (sundae) - blood sausage	7	6.4
비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice	96	87.3
김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish	98	89.1
라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles	102	92.7
치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken	98	89.1
순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew	37	33.6
떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake	92	83.6
장조림 (jangjorim) - soy sauce braised quail eggs	22	20
자장면 (jjangmyeon) - black bean noodles	67	60.9
미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup	29	26.4
비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles	11	10
붕어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste	37	33.6
김밥 (gimbap) - seaweed rice roll	86	78.2
계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet	75	68.2

Table 10: Screener Question: Frequently eaten Korean food.

As shown in **Table 10**, at least 60% of those polled reported having consumed almost all of the Korean food featured in the selected K-dramas in the survey. Thus, these partially go in congruence with the researcher's claim that K-dramas do have an

impact on Korean food consumption, preference, and purchase intention of Generation Z viewers.

Do you observe the presence of Korean food in Korean dramas (K-dramas)?

Observation	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	109	99.1
No	1	0.9
TOTAL	110	100.0

Table 11: Screener Question: Observation of Korean cuisine's inclusion in K-dramas.

99.1% of those polled indicated they observe the presence of Korean food in K-dramas, and only one (0.9%) said they do not. This finding is beneficial for discovering the possible impacts of watching K-dramas on Generation Z viewers' Korean food consumption, preferences, and purchase intentions.

Korean Food Consumption and Preference

The following section reveals the extent to which Generation Z's consumption and preferences of Korean food are influenced by their viewing of Korean dramas.

Reliability of Scales

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.83732354 ~ 0.84	8

Figure 7: Reliability Statistics of Korean Food Consumption and Preference Scale.

The Cronbach's Alpha test revealed that the questionnaire scale for this section has "good" internal consistency, indicating that it is reliable.

Respondents' Level of Korean Food Consumption and Preference

Indicators		Mean	SD
1.	Korean drama helps me to appreciate Korean food.	4.48	0.674
2.	I became interested in Korean food because of Korean dramas.	4.41	0.902
3.	I crave to taste/eat Korean food presented in Korean dramas.	4.44	0.862
4.	I consume Korean food the way they are presented in Korean drama.	3.85	0.921
5.	It has become a habit for me to eat Korean food after watching Korean dramas.	3.17	1.180
6.	I choose Korean food featured in Korean dramas over those that are not.	3.47	1.081
7.	I prefer Korean food over other non-local food (e.g., Japanese, Chinese, Thai, and Vietnamese food) from watching Korean dramas.	3.04	1.196
8.	I consume Korean food as part of socializing with peers, friends, and colleagues who watch Korean dramas.	3.64	1.098
OVERALL		3.81	0.180

Note: Verbal Interpretation of Mean: Strongly Agree ~ Very Influential (4.20 - 5.00), Agree ~ Influential (3.40 - 4.19), Neutral (2.60 - 3.39), Disagree ~ Uninfluential (1.80 - 2.59), Strongly Disagree ~ Very Uninfluential (1.00- 1.79).

Table 12: Respondents' Level of Korean Food Consumption and Preference.

The level of Korean food consumption and preference are represented in **Table 12**. It revealed that out of eight (8) indicators of the level of Korean food consumption and preference, respondents strongly agreed with three (3), agreed with three (3), and were neutral with two (2).

The indicator "Korean drama helps me to appreciate Korean food" garnered the highest mean (Mean = 4.48, SD = 0.674). Following this, the indicators "I became interested in Korean food because of Korean dramas" and "I crave to taste/eat Korean food presented in Korean dramas" have the next highest averages with respective means of 4.41 (SD = 0.902) and 4.44 (SD = 0.862). These results stipulate that K-dramas strongly influence the viewer's appreciation and interest in Korean gourmet and consequently their consumption and preference.

Further, the indicators "I choose Korean food featured in Korean dramas over those that are not" and "I prefer Korean food over other non-local food (e.g., Japanese, Chinese, Thai, and Vietnamese food)" measured the influence of Korean dramas on viewers' food preferences. These indicators yielded the corresponding means of 3.47 (SD = 1.081) and 3.04 (SD = 1.196). The verbal interpretation for the indicators "agree"

and “neutral” come into conflict when the most dominant is looked for by the researcher. However, the interpretations "agree" and "neutral" may suggest that the respondents consider Korean food featured in K-dramas preferable to those that are not and other non-local foreign cuisine.

The indicator "I consume Korean food as part of socializing with peers, friends, and colleagues who watch Korean dramas" then focuses on how K-drama affects individuals' subjective norms regarding eating Korean food. As interpreted, it yielded "agree" as it received a mean of 3.64 (SD = 1.098). This shows that subjective norms also have a huge impact on drawing one’s preference and consumption of Korean food.

Using the five-point scale with 4.20 - 5.00 as Strongly Agree ~ Very Influential, 3.40 - 4.19 as Agree ~ Influential, 2.60 - 3.39 as Neutral, 1.80 - 2.59 as Disagree ~ Uninfluential, 1.00 - 1.79 as Strongly Disagree ~ Very Uninfluential, the overall mean scores for this section was 3.81 (SD = 0.180), indicating that the respondents "agree" that K-dramas are "influential" and significantly affect their consumption and preference of Korean food.

Korean Food Purchase Intention

The following section reveals the extent to which Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food is influenced by their viewing of Korean dramas.

Reliability of Scales

Cronbach’s Alpha	Number of Items
0.847363654 ~ 0.85	6

Figure 8: Reliability Statistics of Korean Food Purchase Intention Scale.

The Cronbach's Alpha test revealed that the questionnaire scale for this section has “good” internal consistency, indicating that it is acceptable.

Respondents' Level of Korean Food Purchase Intention

Indicators		Mean	SD
1.	I purchase Korean food shown in Korean dramas.	4.02	0.867
2.	I purchase Korean food featured in Korean dramas out of curiosity.	4.21	0.836
3.	I am guided in purchasing Korean food by watching Korean dramas.	3.96	0.938
4.	I take extra effort to locate and buy Korean food shown in Korean dramas.	3.25	1.161
5.	I include Korean food in my regular food purchases.	3.09	1.193
6.	I buy Korean food to share my experiences with others who also enjoy Korean dramas and to encourage them to do the same.	3.54	1.114
OVERALL		3.68	0.157

Note: Verbal Interpretation of Mean: Strongly Agree ~ Very Influential (4.20 - 5.00), Agree ~ Influential (3.40 - 4.19), Neutral (2.60 - 3.39), Disagree ~ Uninfluential (1.80 - 2.59), Strongly Disagree ~ Very Uninfluential (1.00- 1.79).

Table 13: Respondents' Level of Korean Food Purchase Intention.

Table 13 presents the respondents' level of Korean Food Purchase Intention. Results show that respondents strongly agree they "[I] purchase Korean food featured in Korean dramas out of curiosity", garnering the highest overall mean of 4.21 (SD = 0.836) among the six (6) indicators. It was followed by "I purchase Korean food shown in Korean dramas" (Mean = 4.02, SD = 0.867) and "I am guided in purchasing Korean food by watching Korean dramas" (Mean = 3.96, SD = 0.938). It can be inferred from these findings that the respondents agree that K-dramas have an impact on their intention to buy Korean food.

On the other hand, the respondents also agree with "I buy Korean food to share my experiences with others who also enjoy Korean dramas and to encourage them to do the same" (Mean = 3.54, SD = 1.114). This finding demonstrates how subjective norms also play a significant role in determining one's purchase intention of Korean food.

Using the five-point scale with 4.20 - 5.00 as Strongly Agree ~ Very Influential, 3.40 - 4.19 as Agree ~ Influential, 2.60 - 3.39 as Neutral, 1.80 - 2.59 as Disagree ~ Uninfluential, 1.00 - 1.79 as Strongly Disagree ~ Very Uninfluential, the respondents "agree" that K-dramas are "influential" and significantly influence their purchase intention of Korean food, as evidenced by the overall mean score of 3.68 (SD = 0.157) for this section.

Influential Korean Dramas

This section will discuss which of the selected Korean dramas had the most influence on viewers' preferences for Korean food, consumption, and purchase intent.

Korean Dramas	Which of the following Korean dramas influenced you to be interested in Korean food? Choose your top 3.		Which of the following Korean dramas compelled you to try and purchase Korean food? Choose your top 3.	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)	82	74.5	74	67.3
Fight For My Way (2017)	28	25.5	29	26.4
Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017)	22	20	26	23.6
What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018)	15	13.6	19	17.3
Crash Landing On You (2019)	27	24.5	29	26.4
Hospital Playlist (2020-2021)	23	20.9	26	23.6
Itaewon Class (2020)	46	41.8	45	40.9
It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020)	8	7.3	8	7.3
Start-Up (2020)	15	13.6	13	11.8
Run-On (2020)	1	0.9	1	0.9
Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021)	19	17.3	17	15.5
My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021)	7	6.4	9	8.2
Vincenzo (2021)	9	8.2	7	6.4
Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)	28	25.5	27	24.5

Table 14: Respondents' Choice of Most Influential K-dramas.

Table 14 shows the respondents' top three (3) Korean dramas that sparked their interest and led them to try and buy Korean food. Most of the respondents answered "Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)" (f = 82, % = 74.5 and f = 74, % = 67.3). It was followed by "Itaewon Class (2020)", which garnered at least 45 responses. The subsequent results apparently mimic a normal distribution of values, in terms of statistics. These are "Fight For My Way (2017)" (f = 28, % = 25.5 and f = 29, % = 26.4), "Crash Landing On You (2019)" (f = 27, % = 24.5 and f = 29, % = 26.4), and "Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)" (f = 28, % = 25.5 and f = 27, % = 24.5). These K-

dramas heavily featured Korean food in their plots, particularly the first two shows. Accordingly, this may be attributed to the inference that specific K-dramas deliver a huge impact on the viewers' choices, consumption, and purchase intent of Korean food.

Korean Food	Which of the following Korean food from the aforementioned Korean dramas caught your attention? Choose your top 3.		Which of the following Korean dishes from the aforementioned Korean dramas made you feel like you had to try them? Choose your top 3.		Which of the following Korean food from the aforementioned Korean dramas are you most likely to choose when you shop for Korean food? Choose your top 3.	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue	81	76.3	55	50	62	56.4
오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake	28	25.5	29	26.4	39	35.5
순대 (sundae) - blood sausage	8	7.3	15	13.6	3	2.7
비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice	29	26.4	24	21.8	19	17.3
김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish	27	24.5	17	15.5	32	29.1
라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles	34	30.9	30	27.3	63	57.3
치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken	39	35.5	32	29.1	39	35.5
순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew	11	10	13	11.8	3	2.7
떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake	25	22.7	9	8.2	2	1.8
장조림 (jangjorim) - soy sauce braised quail eggs	4	3.6	25	22.7	31	28.2
자장면 (jjangmyeon) - black bean noodles	20	18.2	25	22.7	8	7.3

미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup	3	2.7	9	8.2	2	1.8
비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles	2	1.8	14	12.7	1	0.9
붕어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste	4	3.6	14	12.7	4	3.6
김밥 (gimbap) - seaweed rice roll	12	10.9	15	13.6	13	11.8
계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet	3	2.7	4	13.6	9	8.2

Table 15: Respondents' Top Korean Food Picks.

Table 15 lists the respondents' top picks for Korean food that was influenced by Korean dramas. Among the three (3) questions presented, three (3) consistent responses were found, and they were “삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue”, “치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken”, “라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles” and “오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake”. These consistent responses from the respondents highlight the fact that viewers' choices, preferences, and plans to purchase Korean food are also heavily influenced by subjective norms.

Research Hypothesis Testing

In light of the findings previously presented, the next section attempts to prove or disprove the listed hypotheses in this paper.

H1: *Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects Generation Z's Korean food preferences and consumption.*

The findings in **Table 12** show that Korean dramas are “influential” on Generation Z's consumption and preference for Korean food (Mean = 3.81, SD =

0.180). Thus, this supports the first hypothesis. Generation Z's Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects their preference and consumption of Korean food.

H2: *Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food.*

As supported by **Table 13**, Korean drama viewership on Netflix was found to be “influential” on Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food (Mean = 3.68, SD = 0.157). Hence, the second hypothesis was confirmed. Therefore, Korean drama viewership on Netflix has a significant effect on Generation Z's purchasing intention of Korean food.

H3: *Certain Korean dramas on Netflix influence Generation Z's food preferences and purchase intentions for Korean food.*

Table 14 revealed that certain Korean dramas have piqued Generation Z's curiosity about Korean food and have led them to try and purchase it. Accordingly, it supports the third hypothesis stating that specific Korean dramas on Netflix influence Generation Z's preferences, consumption, and purchase intentions for Korean food.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary and Conclusions

Given the meticulous planning and strategic thinking displayed in Chapter 1 of this research, the necessary support for the endeavor with the pertinent data and information found in Chapter 2, the methodological approach used to conduct the research in Chapter 3, and the data collection and analysis presented in Chapter 4, this chapter intends to sum up and conclude the main objectives of the study.

Summary

Interesting findings were obtained from the statistical analysis of the data collected for this study. As shown in Chapter 4, firstly, Generation Z's preference for and consumption of Korean food is significantly influenced by their viewing of Korean dramas on Netflix. Further, responses regarding the influence of Korean drama on purchasing intentions were also noted as significant. Lastly, some Korean dramas actually sparked viewers' interest in trying and buying Korean food. These findings have led to a better understanding of how Generation Z viewers' choices of Korean food and intent to purchase it are influenced by their viewing of Korean dramas.

Conclusions

This paper examined the perceived influence of Korean dramas on the purchase intentions of Korean food by Generation Z college students in the National Capital Region. The study measured the consumption, preference, and purchase intention of the respondents. These were evaluated using the quantitative responses and the AIDA Model presented in Chapter 2 of this paper.

- a. **Objective 1:** *To determine the extent to which Korean dramas influence Generation Z's food choices.*

The study found that Korean dramas significantly influence the perception and preference of Korean food of Generation Z college

students in the National Capital Region. This comes in congruent with the results presented in **Table 12**, discussed in Chapter 4. Based on these results, it can reach the second and third level of Lewis' AIDA Model — *interest and desire* (for the case of the material, it allows the viewers to have a greater liking for the Korean food presented).

- b. **Objective 2:** *To investigate how quickly Generation Z purchases Korean food after seeing it on Korean television shows on Netflix.*

The purchase tendency of Korean food is effectively tapped by watching Korean dramas. This finding goes in congruence with the responses gathered in the survey. Accordingly, this exhibits a clear potential of Korean dramas to reach the fourth and last level of Lewis' AIDA Model — *action* (for the case of the material, it has fully persuaded the viewers to purchase the Korean food featured in the Korean drama).

- c. **Objective 3:** *To determine which Korean television shows on Netflix significantly impact Generation Z's purchase intention on Korean food.*

As demonstrated in Chapter 4, some Korean dramas on Netflix have an impact on viewers' perceptions of and decisions to purchase Korean food. On this note, Korean dramas reach the first and second levels of Lewis' AIDA Model — *attention and interest* (for the case of the material, it allows the viewers to recognize the featured Korean food).

All told, through the quantitative analysis and the concept of Lewis' AIDA Model, Korean dramas presented on Netflix are generally influential to Generation Z college students in the National Capital Region under different multiple extents (i.e., preference, consumption, and purchase intention). This proves that the *Hallyu* wave in the Philippines is heavily influenced by mass media, particularly digital media (in this case, Netflix). The viewers' intense preference for Korean food is one example of its influence on people.

Recommendations

The primary goal of this research is to significantly advance any academic fields that are interested in or connected to the subject under discussion. However, it also hopes to introduce fresh viewpoints, concepts, and ideas to a variety of academic fields as well as potential participants and beneficiaries who might find the study's findings useful.

Area Involvement

The *Hallyu* wave that is currently sweeping the globe, particularly the Philippines, has an impact on a large number of people. However, this project was limited to Korean dramas presented on Netflix. As a result, future researchers may look into different aspects of the *Hallyu* wave, such as Korean pop music (K-pop), Korean movies, Korean variety shows, Korean games, and the like, to further understand the influence of the *Hallyu* wave on people across the world.

Nominal Extents

As it relates to this study, the nominal extents of preference, consumption, and purchase intention of Korean food were the only ones included in the survey. On this note, future researchers may want to investigate and study additional potential extents and aspects like similarity with local food and Korean beverages (e.g., soju). With this, a wider range of viewers and audiences may be accommodated, which can aid in expanding and improving the study.

Other Streaming Platforms

This study focused on Korean dramas presented on Netflix. Another recommendation is to use and explore other streaming platforms that cater to Korean dramas, such as Amazon Prime, Apple TV, and Disney+. Others may also look into Korean dramas that are available for free streaming on websites like YouTube. Data collection for these will aid in discovering additional novel and unexpected insights into the impact of Korean dramas on viewers.

Study Population and Statistical Analysis

Participants in this study were limited to those who are current college students in the National Capital Region. The researcher was constrained to this group and may have had limited answers, making it challenging to generalize the study's results. Future researchers may investigate a larger study population to gather more data, which could facilitate generalization and improve comprehension of the study. Likewise, to further establish the impact of Korean dramas, the proponent suggests using additional, more detailed research methodologies. For instance, they can use inferential statistics to draw generalizations about the population which the sample or respondents represent. With this, it could lead to a deeper comprehension of the topic.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Survey Matrix

Research Questions	Research Objectives	Hypotheses	Survey Questionnaire
<p>1. How strongly do Korean dramas influence Generation Z's Korean food consumption and preference?</p>	<p>To determine the extent to which Korean dramas influence Generation Z's food choices.</p>	<p>Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects Generation Z's Korean food preferences.</p>	<p>Please indicate the extent to which each statement applies to you with the following indicators:</p> <p>5 – Strongly Agree 4 – Agree 3 – Neutral 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Korean drama helps me to appreciate Korean food. 2. I became interested in Korean food because of Korean dramas. 3. I crave to taste/eat Korean food presented in Korean dramas. 4. I consume Korean food the way they are presented in Korean drama. 5. It has become a habit for me to eat Korean food after watching Korean dramas. 6. I choose Korean food featured in Korean dramas over those that are not. 7. I prefer Korean food over other non-local food (e.g. Japanese, Chinese, Thai, and Vietnamese food) from watching Korean dramas. 8. I consume Korean food as part of socializing with peers, friends, and colleagues who watch Korean dramas.
<p>2. How strongly do Korean dramas influence Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food?</p>	<p>To investigate how quickly Generation Z purchases Korean food after seeing it on Korean television shows on Netflix.</p>	<p>Korean drama viewership on Netflix significantly affects Generation Z's purchase intention of Korean food.</p>	<p>Please indicate the extent to which each statement applies to you with the following indicators:</p> <p>5 – Strongly Agree 4 – Agree 3 – Neutral 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I purchase Korean food shown in Korean dramas. 2. I purchase Korean food featured in Korean dramas out of curiosity.

			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. I am guided in purchasing Korean food by watching Korean dramas. 4. I take extra effort to locate and purchase Korean food shown in Korean dramas. 5. I include Korean food in my regular food purchases. 6. I buy Korean food to share my experiences with others who also enjoy Korean dramas and to encourage them to do the same.
<p>3. Which Korean drama television shows influence the purchase intention of Korean food most?</p>	<p>To determine which Korean television shows on Netflix significantly impact Generation Z's purchase intention on Korean food.</p>	<p>Certain Korean dramas on Netflix influence Generation Z's food preferences and purchase intentions for Korean food.</p>	<p>Choose from the list to indicate your answer. Choose your top 3.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cheese in the Trap (2016) ● Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016) ● Fight For My Way (2017) ● Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017) ● What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018) ● Crash Landing On You (2019) ● Hospital Playlist (2020-2021) ● Itaewon Class (2020) ● It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020) ● Start-Up (2020) ● Run On (2020) ● Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021) ● My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021) ● Vincenzo (2021) ● Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which of the following Korean dramas influenced you to be interested in Korean food? 2. Which of the following Korean dramas compelled you to try and purchase Korean food? <p>Choose from the list to indicate your answer. Select your top 3.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 삼각김밥 (samgak kimbap) - triangle kimbap ● 삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue ● 오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake ● 김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish ● 비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice ● 라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake ● 순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew ● 족발 (jokbal) - braised pig's trotters ● 비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles ● 미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup ● 붕어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste ● 계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which of the following Korean food from the aforementioned Korean dramas caught your attention? 2. Which of the following Korean dishes from the aforementioned Korean dramas made you feel like you had to try them? 3. Which of the following Korean food from the aforementioned Korean dramas are you most likely to choose when you shop for Korean food?
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APPENDIX B

Survey Instrument

Greetings of peace!

I am Alexis Candano, a student from the University of the Philippines Open University, in the Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies program. As indicated by the title of this form, I am currently conducting a quantitative study that seeks to determine the impact of Korean dramas on Netflix on the purchase intentions and food preferences of Korean food among Generation Z in the Philippines.

Considering the aforementioned objectives, I am looking for participants who meet the qualifications below. If you qualify for this study, I kindly ask you to participate in the survey.

Qualifications:

- **Must be between the ages of 18 - 25.**
- **Must be a current college student within National Capital Region.**
- **Has eaten AT LEAST THREE of the following Korean food (i.e., samgyupsal, kimchi, ramyeon, Korean fried chicken, fish cake, gimbap, bibimbap, tteokbokki, sundubu jiggae, jokbal, bibimguksu, miyeokguk, bunggeopang, gyeran-mari, jangjorim, sundae).**
- **Has watched AT LEAST THREE of the following Korean dramas on Netflix:**
 - *Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)*
 - *Fight For My Way (2017)*
 - *Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017)*
 - *What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018)*
 - *Crash Landing On You (2019)*
 - *Hospital Playlist (2020-2021)*
 - *Itaewon Class (2020)*
 - *It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020)*
 - *Start-Up (2020)*
 - *Run On (2020)*
 - *Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021)*
 - *My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021)*
 - *Vincenzo (2021)*
 - *Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)*

Per the Data Privacy Act of 2012, any information disclosed will only be used for research purposes and kept completely confidential. Likewise, participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time if you wish to do so.

For any questions, concerns, or clarifications, you may contact me through email at alcandano@up.edu.ph. Thank you very much!

PART 1: Demographic profile of the respondents.

Please fill in the following information and select the appropriate circle.

1. Age
 - 18
 - 19
 - 20
 - 21
 - 22
 - 23
 - 24
 - 25

2. Sex
 - Male
 - Female

3. Current Location
 - Caloocan
 - Makati
 - Mandaluyong
 - Manila
 - Malabon
 - Marikina
 - Muntinlupa
 - Navotas
 - Las Piñas
 - Pasay
 - Parañaque
 - Pateros
 - Quezon City
 - San Juan
 - Taguig
 - Valenzuela

4. College or University (Please DO NOT abbreviate, e.g. University of the Philippines; Ateneo de Manila University, De La Salle University, University of Santo Tomas, etc):

5. Current Year-Level
 - 1st Year
 - 2nd Year
 - 3rd Year
 - 4th Year
 - 5th Year
 - 6th Year

PART 2: Screener Questions.

1. When did you start watching Korean dramas (K-dramas) on Netflix?
 - 2016
 - 2017
 - 2018
 - 2019
 - 2020
 - 2021
 - 2022
 - 2023

2. How often do you watch Korean dramas (K-Dramas) on Netflix?
 - Daily
 - Once a week
 - Twice a week
 - Thrice a week
 - Once a month
 - Once every 3 months
 - Once every 6 months
 - Once every 12 months

3. How many hours do you spend per day watching Korean dramas (K-dramas) on Netflix?
 - Less than an hour
 - 1 - 2 hours
 - 3 - 6 hours
 - 7 - 9 hours
 - 10 - 12 hours
 - More than 12 hours

4. What device/s do you use to access Netflix? (Select all that apply).
 - Mobile phone
 - Tablet
 - Computer (i.e., laptop, desktop)
 - Television

5. Which of the following K-dramas have you watched on Netflix? (Select all that apply).
 - Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)
 - Fight For My Way (2017)
 - Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017)
 - What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018)
 - Crash Landing On You (2019)
 - Hospital Playlist (2020-2021)
 - Itaewon Class (2020)
 - It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020)
 - Start-Up (2020)
 - Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021)
 - My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021)

- o Vincenzo (2021)
 - o Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)
6. Which of the following Korean food have you eaten or are familiar with? (Select all that apply).
- o 삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue
 - o 오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake
 - o 순대 (sundae) - blood sausage
 - o 비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice
 - o 김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish
 - o 라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles
 - o 치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken
 - o 순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew
 - o 장조림 (jangjorim) - soy sauce braised quail eggs
 - o 떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake
 - o 자장면 (jjangmyeon) - black bean noodles
 - o 미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup
 - o 비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles
 - o 봉어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste
 - o 김밥 (gimbap) - seaweed rice roll
 - o 계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet
7. Do you observe the presence of Korean food in Korean dramas?
- o Yes
 - o No

PART 3: Korean Food Consumption and Preference.

Please indicate the extent to which each statement applies to you with the following indicators:

- 5 – Strongly Agree
- 4 – Agree
- 3 – Neutral
- 2 – Disagree
- 1 – Strongly Disagree

	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	Korean drama helps me to appreciate Korean food.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	I became interested in Korean food because of Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	I crave to taste/eat Korean food presented in Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	I consume Korean food the way they are presented in Korean drama.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	It has become a habit for me to eat Korean food after watching Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
6.	I choose Korean food featured in Korean dramas over those that are not.	5	4	3	2	1
7.	I prefer Korean food over other non-local food (e.g. Japanese, Chinese, Thai, and Vietnamese food) from watching Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
8.	I consume Korean food as part of socializing with peers, friends, and colleagues who watch Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1

PART 4: Korean Food Purchase Intention

Please indicate the extent to which each statement applies to you with the following indicators:

5 – Strongly Agree

4 – Agree

3 – Neutral

2 – Disagree
 1 – Strongly Disagree

	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	I purchase Korean food shown in Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
2.	I purchase Korean food featured in Korean dramas out of curiosity.	5	4	3	2	1
3.	I am guided in purchasing Korean food by watching Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
4.	I take extra effort to locate and buy Korean food shown in Korean dramas.	5	4	3	2	1
5.	I include Korean food in my regular food purchases.	5	4	3	2	1
6.	I buy Korean food to share my experiences with others who also enjoy Korean dramas and to encourage them to do the same.	5	4	3	2	1

PART 5. Influential Korean Dramas

Choose from the list to indicate your answer.

1. Which of the following Korean dramas **influenced you to be interested** in Korean food? [Choose your top 3].
 - o Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)
 - o Fight For My Way (2017)
 - o Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017)
 - o What’s Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018)
 - o Crash Landing On You (2019)
 - o Hospital Playlist (2020-2021)
 - o Itaewon Class (2020)
 - o It’s Okay Not To Be Okay (2020)
 - o Start-Up (2020)
 - o Run On (2020)

- o Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021)
 - o My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021)
 - o Vincenzo (2021)
 - o Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)
2. Which of the following Korean dramas compelled you to **try and purchase** Korean food? [Choose your top 3].
- o Weightlifting Fairy Kim Bok Joo (2016)
 - o Fight For My Way (2017)
 - o Strong Girl Bong-soon (2017)
 - o What's Wrong With Secretary Kim? (2018)
 - o Crash Landing On You (2019)
 - o Hospital Playlist (2020-2021)
 - o Itaewon Class (2020)
 - o It's Okay Not To Be Okay (2020)
 - o Start-Up (2020)
 - o Run On (2020)
 - o Hometown Cha-Cha-Cha (2021)
 - o My Roommate is a Gumiho (2021)
 - o Vincenzo (2021)
 - o Extraordinary Attorney Woo (2022)
3. Which of the following Korean food from the aforementioned Korean dramas **caught your attention**? [Choose your top 3].
- o 삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue
 - o 오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake
 - o 순대 (sundae) - blood sausage
 - o 비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice
 - o 김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish
 - o 라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles
 - o 치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken
 - o 순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew
 - o 장조림 (jangjorim) - soy sauce braised quail eggs
 - o 떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake
 - o 자장면 (jjangmyeon) - black bean noodles
 - o 미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup
 - o 비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles
 - o 봉어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste
 - o 김밥 (gimbap) - seaweed rice roll

- o 계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet
4. Which of the following Korean dishes from the aforementioned Korean dramas **made you feel like you had to try them?** [Choose your top 3].
- o 삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue
 - o 오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake
 - o 순대 (sundae) - blood sausage
 - o 비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice
 - o 김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish
 - o 라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles
 - o 치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken
 - o 순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew
 - o 장조림 (jangjorim) - soy sauce braised quail eggs
 - o 떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake
 - o 자장면 (jjangmyeon) - black bean noodles
 - o 미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup
 - o 비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles
 - o 붕어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste
 - o 김밥 (gimbap) - seaweed rice roll
 - o 계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet
5. Which of the following Korean food from the aforementioned Korean dramas are you **most likely to choose** when you shop for Korean food? [Choose your top 3].
- o 삼겹살 (samgyeopsal) - Korean barbecue
 - o 오뎅 (odeng) - fish cake
 - o 순대 (sundae) - blood sausage
 - o 비빔밥 (bibimbap) - mixed rice
 - o 김치 (kimchi) - fermented cabbage side dish
 - o 라면 (ramyeon) - instant noodles
 - o 치킨 (chicken) - Korean fried chicken
 - o 순두부찌개 (sundubu jiggae) - soft tofu stew
 - o 장조림 (jangjorim) - soy sauce braised quail eggs
 - o 떡볶이 (tteokbokki) - stir-fried rice cake

- o 자장면 (jjangmyeon) - black bean noodles
- o 미역국 (miyeokguk) - seaweed soup
- o 비빔국수 (bibimguksu) - cold spicy noodles
- o 붕어빵 (bunggeopang) - pastry with red bean paste
- o 김밥 (gimbap) - seaweed rice roll
- o 계란말이 (gyeran-mari) - rolled omelet

APPENDIX C

Data Tabulation of Survey Questionnaire (Nominal Extents)

Korean Food Preference and Consumption					
	IF 5	IF 4	IF 3	IF 2	IF 1
Question 1	62	38	8	1	1
Question 2	68	26	10	5	1
Question 3	69	25	12	3	1
Question 4	28	47	26	8	1
Question 5	20	19	39	24	8
Question 6	24	27	39	17	3
Question 7	17	18	38	26	11
Question 8	25	42	27	10	6
TOTAL					
	313	242	199	94	32

Korean Food Purchase Intention					
	IF 5	IF 4	IF 3	IF 2	IF 1
Question 1	34	51	19	5	1
Question 2	44	52	8	5	1
Question 3	34	49	17	9	1
Question 4	20	22	36	25	7
Question 5	17	23	32	29	9
Question 6	22	41	27	14	6
TOTAL					
	171	238	139	87	25